

METHODS OF HISTORY TEACHING AND THEIR CLASSIFICATION

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Abstract: The term "teaching technique" refers to a strategy used by the teacher and pupils to work together toward a certain educational objective. In this essay, local and international sources are used to assess the characteristics of the development of history teaching methods in accordance with human growth. The characterisation of teaching methods as inductive, analytical, and other logical approaches is appropriate since the classification of teaching methods is sometimes based on logical operations such analysis and synthesis, deduction, and induction.

Key words: History, historiography, historical teaching methods, historical categories of thought, people and societies, knowledge, skills, and competency

INTRODUCTION

The teacher's instruction and the pupils' learning or cognitive activity are structured through teaching methods and procedures. The term "teaching methods" refers to the process of instructing students based on the active thinking of the teacher, the students' acquisition of scientific knowledge and their capacity to apply it in practice, the development of worldviews and beliefs, mental and physical work, and skills. It also refers to techniques that aid students in developing skills, expanding their knowledge, and developing their creative faculties.

The term "teaching technique" refers to strategies used by the teacher and pupils to work together toward a certain educational objective. In other words, teaching methods are the synthesis of both activities, i.e., the teacher providing

students with knowledge, skills, and abilities, the students doing the same, and the teacher educating the students morally and instilling in them a scientific worldview. comprises the techniques employed in the pursuit of scientific knowledge, abilities, and competencies. The improvement of educational content, reinforcement of educational direction, and activation of teaching strategies were the three main objectives of the reform of the system of secondary general education and secondary special education. Now, in addition to the meticulous learning of ready-made knowledge, skills, and abilities collected by mankind, the curriculum of education should contain creative activities that can assure the growth of students' autonomous thinking and creative abilities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

In order to teach students to think critically and creatively, as well as to develop the required skills and competences in them, teaching strategies are crucial, according to the principles guiding the development of education. The correct resolution of this complicated issue will have a significant impact on the responsible tasks in the secondary general education and special education systems. warm liq. The system of history teaching methods, in particular, has not yet been fully developed, which is a significant issue with teaching approach. Methodists have varied interpretations and categories for "Method" and "Methodical techniques" in the methodological literature. There are significant flaws in the practice of teaching history in the general secondary education and secondary special education systems as a result of the inadequate development of the system of individual and community education methods in the teaching methodology and the absence of a single opinion in this area. Many times, teachers select their teaching strategies for both in-class and extracurricular activities by merely considering pre-existing knowledge, which is educating them (one part of education). They disregard critical circumstances like planning and directing students' learning, which is the second crucial component of education, and steadily increasing their students' knowledge, skills, and abilities.

Among other grave faults, the failure to take into consideration the characteristics of the educational material's content, its educational tasks, and the students' knowledge and skills when selecting the methods and teaching methods. This circumstance has some detrimental effects on the outcomes of general educational work as well as the decline in student interest in the topic of personality and society. Simultaneously, in the application of the secondary education system and secondary special education, particularly in the years to come, in the sphere of educating students through the study of history, carrying out its instruction on a scientific foundation, and enhancing the efficacy of educational activity. Numerous best practices have been compiled and distilled. This work offers the chance to develop a system of instructional strategies and sociological methodological approaches for individuals and society on a scientific basis and to successfully apply them in practice. It is one of the crucial prerequisites and ways to increase the effectiveness and quality of knowledge. At various points during the teaching of pedagogy, the problem of classifying teaching methods on a scientific foundation was resolved in a variety of ways. Teaching techniques are categorized as inductive, analytical, and other logical techniques. This classification of teaching techniques is sometimes based on logical activities like analysis and synthesis, deduction, and induction.

It is sometimes advised to group instructional strategies according to the degree of student activity and cognitive function. This distinction focuses more on the overall character of instruction than on specific teaching strategies. The movement from in-person observation to abstract thought and from there to practice forms the methodological foundation of the theory of techniques. As a foundation for teaching strategies, the pedagogy of the 1960s gave enormous weight to the sources of information on the subject being studied (the teacher's live speech, instructiveness, and texts). In their studies, Leningrad scientists published in 1966, clearly described the problem of categorizing instructional approaches by sources of information. By the end of the 1950s, the methodology of teaching history began to categorize

instructional techniques depending on the sources of students' prior knowledge. On the basis of the sources of education, or the sources of knowledge, Methodist P.S. Leibengrub demonstrates the following techniques of teaching people and society in the system of general secondary education and secondary special education.

- 1) the story-and-lecture approach;
- 2) the interview method;
- 3) the instructional method;
- 4) the working with the textbook method;
- 5) the working with historical documents method; and
- 6) the employing fiction method.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

For whatever reason, P. S. Leibengrub requires that any oral presentation technique include both a story and a lecture.

The following three groups comprise his division of teaching techniques:

- 1) Living speech: a narrative, a definition or description, a problem statement;
- 2) Instructional methods: visual aids such photographs and other teaching aids, graphic notes written on the board, technological aids, etc.; and
- 3) Text-based approaches.

A. Vagin provides a table outlining the classification of teaching strategies based on the sources and modes of knowledge as well as how the sources of knowledge are used in the key phases of the teaching process in line with didactic requirements. This table makes it very evident that depending on the subject matter addressed in each class, several teaching techniques must be used. The teaching profession. The teaching strategies suggested by A. Vagin are quite realistic, as evidenced by recent history in both general education and secondary special education systems. In his work titled "Issue of the system of educational methods and methodical techniques," Professor P.V. Gora suggests methods and methodical approaches that are inextricably linked to the teaching of the teacher and the learning

of pupils (cognitive activity). This analysis' classification of teaching strategies offers a chance to give teachers the in-depth knowledge and essential abilities they need. It also enables the teacher to support the students by considering the instructional material's substance as well as their knowledge, skills, and capacities. Based on his experience teaching history in the general secondary education and secondary special education systems, P.V. Gora classified teaching techniques for history from both a didactic and historical-methodical perspective. Educational history demonstrates the importance of giving the educational tasks of the material and its unique features the attention they deserve. P.V. Gora is founded on the same tenet, in which it is demonstrated the necessity of using the educational material's substance and the aim for learning it as a basis, and approaching and resolving the issue with a historicalmethodical criterion. The goal cannot be accomplished by merely outlining the information that students need to retain, so care should be used while selecting methods and teaching strategies. It is essential to instruct pupils while also stimulating their cognitive activity and preparing them for practical actions. They need to improve their thirst for creativity, learn to conduct autonomous, creative research, identify previously unknown to society ways of knowing, and be able to put such discoveries into practice.

I. Y. Lerner categorizes instructional strategies into 5 types.

1. The description-illustration approach;
2. The reproductive approach;
3. The research approach;
4. The partial search or heuristic approach; and
5. Problem-based learning or problem-based teaching

Students can carefully memorize and retell the stuff they have studied using the first and second methods of instruction. You merely need to be able to memorize them in order to understand the ready-made knowledge that the teacher is explaining. The key benefit of this approach is that it encourages students to pay attention and

learn a lot of historical information in a short amount of time. However, this approach cannot guarantee that students' thinking, knowledge, skills, and capacities will develop or that they will become interested in studying history, particularly high school pupils. The second method—problem-based learning or problem-based teaching—is more efficient than the first. In other words, while the teacher explains the historical knowledge to the students, he makes them think about this knowledge, activates their thinking activity, and increases their interest. The teacher poses challenging questions to the students, and together with them, he finds solutions to the problems. As they complete challenging and logical tasks with the help of their teacher, students gain the ability to think for themselves. All of this will aid pupils in developing their critical thinking and research work fundamentals. Additionally, utilizing a variety of techniques, educational and inspection work is done. First and foremost, it should be assumed that teaching methods include both those used by teachers to instruct their pupils and those used by students to learn or engage in cognitive activity. In reality, the teacher encourages the students' thinking and learning while describing or doing certain practical acts with the use of instructional materials. guides their acquisition of information and abilities as they learn the subject matter. The following is a description of teaching methods that are based on teaching and learning methods and the associated mental activity of teachers and students. Teaching strategies include approaches to assist students develop skills and competencies, expand their knowledge, and develop their creative and critical thinking skills. Students learn and apply scientific knowledge while working under the guidance of their teachers.

Teaching and learning strategies as well as teacher and student-led thinking activities are common and significant aspects of these systems. The following groups can be used to categorize related teaching strategies.

- a) oral instruction;
- b) instruction using printed texts;

- c) instructional technique; and
- d) practical method.

The interplay between teaching strategies and various forms of students' cognitive activity, as well as their influence on one another, results in the interdependence of approaches within a system. The secondary education system, which includes secondary special education, has found that instructional teaching is virtually never employed without a teacher's explanation, and that the teacher's explanation always makes use of instructional resources. The use of technological tools, texts, and other practical tasks by students is directly tied to instructional and oral learning strategies. All secondary education courses, including those in the secondary special education system, can be taught using this methodology. But depending on the unique characteristics of the content of each educational subject, particularly the subject of history, and its educational tasks, each of them is used in a different methodological style.

CONCLUSION

The educational process, in which the teacher and students take an active part, combines teaching methods and students' learning (cognitive activity) approaches in a variety of ways to build a coherent methodology. Achieving a successful outcome in the process of education and teaching methods is unattainable if any one of this group of methods is ignored. While teaching and learning strategies are a part of educational strategies, they also comprise analogous strategies that are compatible with the critical thinking skills and personalities of teachers and students. But there is a relationship between teaching methods and educational approaches, with some significant similarities and differences. Teaching strategies are distinct from the didactic approaches used in all academic courses in this regard. Thus, in order to properly implement the educational tasks of the material, the teacher should appropriately select methodological approaches (teaching and learning methods) that are in conformity with the content of the educational material. It is well known

that deciding on the lesson's and the activity's educational tasks comes first in the preparation for each class and extracurricular activity. The teacher's level of theoretical knowledge and the extent to which he has mastered the system of methodical methods will determine his ability to choose methodical methods that support the implementation of educational tasks correctly and on a scientific basis in accordance with the content of the educational material.

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